

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D6.3 – Report on Dissemination and Communication actions and their impact 1

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About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Abstract	The D6.3, Report on Dissemination and Communication actions and their impact 1, presents the initial efforts of UP2030 to disseminate the activities conducted and raise awareness regarding the project. In the document are included all the activities performed the first six months of UP2030, the materials produced, the tools utilized to increase the visibility of the project and the evaluation of their progress.			

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Executive Summary

The present deliverable provides a detailed report on the progress towards the implementation of the dissemination strategy and plan presented in the deliverable D6.1 “Dissemination and Communication Strategy”. Therefore, this document has a similar structure and aims to give updates on the dissemination and communication (D&C) activities performed, the channels used, and the results achieved during the first six months of the project.

The scope of these activities is to maximise the impact and the awareness of UP2030. The report includes the objectives of the activities, promotional tools and materials developed, and a description of the project website. Moreover, an updated procedure for monitoring the performance of the individual partners and of the project as regards the dissemination actions is described. All tools presented in this document are being used to raise awareness at EU level and beyond, acting principally as the brand guidelines of the project. Also, the deliverable reports all the actions that have been concluded up to M6 for the dissemination of the project.

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
D	Deliverable
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
Mx	Month x
WP	Work package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The purpose of this document is to monitor the UP2030 dissemination and communication (D&C) activities presented in D6.1 in M3 by conducting the initial report and evaluating their impact. It includes all the relevant information to facilitate the execution and control of the different tasks and opportunities of the activities related to D&C of the project and the activities performed the first six months, from January 2023 to June 2023 (M1-M6). Furthermore, it includes information regarding the channels used so far, monitoring procedures, communication policies, and other essential information needed to facilitate the cooperation and exchange of information among partners in an efficient and agile manner.

1.2 Document Structure

This document, is organised according to the following structure:

- Section 1: Introduction - describing the purpose, the scope of the document and its structure.
- Section 2: Dissemination activities – presenting the dissemination activities performed the first six months and the individual dissemination plan.
- Section 3: Communication tools and activities – referring to the project website, social media presence, newsletters, press releases and press kit.
- Section 4: Dissemination and Communication Monitoring – presenting the monitoring files for dissemination and communication activities and related indicators.
- Section 5: Dissemination and Communication Planned Activities
- Section 6: Conclusions, including a summary and future work recommendations.

Dissemination and communication activities performed the first 6 months.

During the first six months of the project, several D&C were fulfilled, specifically:

- the design of the visual identity of the project and relevant materials (M1).
- the development of the project website (M3).
- the creation of the social media accounts and the first posts (M1).
- the publication of the first press release (M4).
- the design of the initial materials for the press kit (M5).
- the participation and organisation of several workshops (mostly related to the initial tasks from WP2 and WP4) and events.
- the effort to build synergies with relevant projects and initiatives.

The aforementioned activities will be further analysed in the upcoming sections of this deliverable.

2 Dissemination activities

The dissemination activities are conducted during the lifespan of UP2030 to maximise the impact of the project results – as described in D6.1 “ Dissemination and Communication Strategy”. Such activities support all work packages (WPs) to increase the visibility of the project, its innovation potential, and its wider impact in general public. The Dissemination and Communication (D&C) activities will prioritize the privacy and anonymity of all participants in UP2030, while adhering to ethical principles, as described in D1.7 - Security, privacy and ethics handbook 1.

2.1.1 Workshops and Events

During the first six months of the project the partners made a remarkable effort to organise several workshops and events, in the framework of the need assessment from WP2 and LAAs from WP4. The majority of them were focused on the pilot cities that participate in UP2030. The tables below present detailed information for each workshop. Specifically, the partners involved, the title of the event, the date, the location, the event website – if available - and a short description.

Table 1 UP2030 performed workshops and events

2.1.1.1 Thematic Workshops from WP2 & WP4

Event 1

Partner	Fraunhofer, USTUTT
Event	1 st UP2030 Workshop in Muenster
Date	24/05/2023
Location	Muenster, Germany
Event website link	N/A
Short description of the event	First Workshop done as liaison for the city of Muenster

Figure 1 UP2030 Muenster workshop

Event 2

Partner	ICA, GRANOLLERS, AQUATEC, UIC
Event	1 st UP2030 Workshop in Granollers
Date	29/03/2023
Location	Granollers, Spain
Event website link	N/A
Short description of the event	First workshop on needs organized for UP2030 with internal stakeholders.
Abstract/ publication related to the event	Publication in LinkedIn (see Section 2)

Figure 2 UP2030 1st Granollers workshop

Event 3

Partner	ICA, GRANOLLERS, AQUATEC, UIC
Event	2 nd UP2030 Workshop in Granollers
Date	06/06/2023
Location	Granollers, Spain
Event website link	N/A
Short description of the event	Second workshop on needs organized for UP2030 with external stakeholders.

Figure 3 2nd UP2030 Granollers workshop

Event 4

Partner	Lisbon, LISBOA E-NOVA, LNEC
Event	Workshop 1: Lisbon Climate resilience 2030: needs and barriers
Date	29/05/2023
Location	Lisbon, Portugal
Event website link	https://www.lisboa.pt/atualidade/noticias/detalhe/resiliencia-climatica-2030-em-debate-em-lisboa/
Short description of the event	<p>Workshop on Climate resilience 2030: needs and barriers, focusing on several topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lisbon and the challenges of Climate Resilience 2030: past, present, and future • How to continue building a better neighbourhood: commitment, participation, and citizenship <p>Quality of life and the urban environment: a close look at the health of residents in Lisbon , a collaborative work and debate with 40 participants.</p>

Figure 4 1st UP2030 Lisbon workshop

Event 5

Partner	Budapest, GGI
Event	1 st UP2030 Workshop in Budapest
Date	27/04/2023
Location	Budapest
Event website link	N/A
Short description of the event	Participants from Budapest transportation companies, urban design companies, landscape architectures and professionals from climate policy departments identified the governance gaps and needs across the 5 dimensions and the expansion of the scope of the stakeholder map.

Figure 5 1st UP2030 Workshop in Budapest

Event 6

Partner	GUNAM, Istanbul
Event	1 st UP2030 Workshop in İstanbul
Date	03/05/2023
Location	İstanbul, Turkey
Event website link	N/A
Short description of the event	First workshop on needs organized for UP2030

Figure 6 1st UP2030 Workshop in İstanbul

Event 7

Partner	Muenster
Event	MultiKlima Transfer Workshop
Date	19/04/2023
Location	Münster, Germany
Event website link	https://www.geo-net.de/de/geo-net/multiklima.html
Short description of the event	The Workshop was planned to transfer the results of the project “MultiKlima”, which was funded by the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection from 1/2018 to 05/2021, to a larger circle of colleagues within the municipality. Several Departments (e.g., environmental planning, green space maintenance, water management planning, historical preservation, planning) were participating and discussing the results and recent planning projects with benefits and barriers towards climate resilient redevelopment of public spaces within the city of Münster.

Figure 7 UP2030 in Multiklima transfer workshop

Event 8

Partner	Muenster
Event	Fast Forward Sustainable: Managing Climate Risks - Is Your Company Climate-Safe Yet?
Date	01/06/2023
Location	Münster, Germany
Event website link	https://www.wfm-muenster.de/veranstaltung/fast-forward-nachhaltig-klimarisiken-managen-ist-ihr-unternehmen-schon-klimasicher/
Short description of the event	At the event organized by the Munster Economic Development Agency was presented the working group on climate adaptation,

	climate impact monitoring and controlling and the Münster's path to becoming a climate-resilient city. Münster's participation in UP2030 was presented during the event.
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Event 9

Partner	Rotterdam, RCities
Event	1 st UP2030 Workshop in Rotterdam
Date	25/05/23
Location	Rotterdam, the Netherlands
Event website link	NA
Short description of the event	First workshop organized for UP2030
Abstract/ publication related to the event	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7070010010507829248

Figure 8 1st UP2030 Rotterdam Workshop

Event 10

Partner	Thessaloniki, MDAT
Event	1 st Engagement Workshop with City Employees
Date	03/05/2023
Location	Thessaloniki
Event website link	Internal invitation via e-mail
Short description of the event	The scope of the event was to inform the city employees about the UP2030 project, the vision for the selected pilot area and specific goals and discuss with them the goals, objectives, the potential barriers, obstacles, driver changes, data available that would help us in the realization of the baseline study.

Figure 9 1st UP2030 Workshop in Thessaloniki

Event 11

Partner	Thessaloniki, MDAT, DRAXIS, RCities
Event	2 nd Engagement Workshop with Local Stakeholders
Date	17/05/2023
Location	Thessaloniki
Event website link	The event was communicated through e-mails
Short description of the event	The 2 nd workshop was focused on informing and involving the local stakeholders in the pilot action plan of the UP2030 project and receive their feedback regarding the needs of the area, the strengths, weaknesses, other active groups that could be involved in the pilot plan as well as opportunities that could help us in the realization of the goals

Figure 10 UP2030 2nd Workshop in Thessaloniki

Event 12

Partner	MfC, Belfast
Event	1 st Stakeholder Workshop - Belfast
Date	24/04/23
Location	Belfast, Northern Ireland, United Kingdom

Event website link	N/A
Short description of the event	<p>First stakeholder workshop organised for UP2030. This was the first in a series of activities that will start to build a 'learning and action alliance' for the neighbourhood which will provide an opportunity to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn about the UP2030 project and the 5UP framework. • Participate in a dialogue on policies, regulations, and codes that need to be updated or replaced to support the transition to climate neutrality. • Build your capacity to deliver actions that promote sustainable urban planning and design. • Develop solution prototypes for selected neighborhoods in Belfast that promote livability and mitigate the impacts of climate change. • Identify opportunities to scale up interventions to achieve city-wide impact. • Share best practices and engage with the Mission to promote sustainable urban planning and design across European cities.
Abstract/ publication related to the event	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7057001880266108928

Figure 11 1st UP2030 Workshop in Belfast

2.1.1.2 Presentation of UP2030 in Exhibitions , Conferences

Event 1

Partner	GUNAM, Istanbul
Event	Solarex İstanbul

Date	04/2023
Location	İstanbul, Turkey
Event website link	Solarexistanbul.com
Short description of the event	Solar Energy Fair
Short description of the abstract/publication	Poster about UP2030 and Oral presentation for participants. Presentation done by ODTÜ-GÜNAM

Figure 12 UP2030 Poster in Solarex Istanbul

Event 2

Partner	GUNAM, Istanbul
Event	Wenergy
Date	05/2023
Location	İzmir, Turkey
Event website link	https://wenergy.com.tr/en/
Short description of the event	Renewable Energy Fair
Short description of the abstract/publication	Emre Demirezen gave basic information about UP2030

Figure 13 UP2030 in Wenergy

Event 3

Partner	Lisbon, LISBOA E-NOVA, LNEC
Event	Community of Practice meeting – SOL (Smart Open Lisbon) Energy Transition
Date	22/03/2023
Location	Lisbon, Portugal
Event website link	N/A
Short description of the event	Community of Practice – several presentations focused on climate changes, followed by discussion and work session on drivers, needs and barriers for reaching carbon neutrality and climate resilience, ensuring a fair and inclusive transition. 20 participants

Figure 14 Community of Practice meeting in Lisbon

Event 4

Partner	Muenster
Event	Final event of the third KlimaTraining
Date	10/05/23
Location	Forum vhs, Münster, Germany
Event website link	https://www.stadt-muenster.de/klima/klimafreundlich-leben
Short description of the event	In the 3rd KlimaTraining ,50 people, from trainees to climate trainers and providers, discussed the evaluation of the climate training in order to continuously improve it. On the other hand, the participants developed new ideas for possible climate training in the district. A short presentation was made about UP2030, focusing on the possibility to implement KlimaTraining in a neighborhood.
Abstract/ publication related to the event	Presentation and documentation
Short description of the abstract/ publication	The presentation shows an introduction to the task in the context of UP2030. The documentation summarises the results of the 5 groups.

Figure 15 UP2030 in KlimaTraining event

2.1.2 Upcoming workshops and events

Table 2 presents the upcoming events that partners of the project might participate or organise the upcoming months. In addition, several workshops and events aligned with the UP2030 activities will be planned by the consortium and they will be reported in D6.4 “Report on Dissemination and Communication actions and their impact 2”.

Table 2 Upcoming events

Title of the event	Date & Venue	Relevant URL	Partners planning to participate
International Conference Paradigm Shifts in Local And Urban Governance	4-6/9/2023, Budapest	https://www.regionalscience.org/index.php/news/upcoming-events/item/3106-igu-cgog-2023-annual-conference,-budapest,-4-6-september-2023.html	FRAUNHOFER, USTUTT
World Smart City Expo	5-8/9/2023, Korea	https://www.worldsmartcityexpo.com/fairDash.do?hl=ENG	FRAUNHOFER, USTUTT
Adaptation Futures 2023	2-6/10/2023, Montreal	https://adaptationfutures.com/	UCCRN, UIC
COP28 UAE	30/11-12/12/2023, Dubai	https://www.cop28.com/en	UCCRN

3rd Global Congress on CLIMATE CHANGE (GCCC-2023)	13-14/9/2023, Barcelona	https://global-climatechange.com/	N/A
Climate City Week	21-29/10/23, Muenster	https://www.stadt-muenster.de/klimastadt/startseite/klimastadt-expo	Muenster
Benicasem conference	20-21/9/2023, Villa Elisa	https://baio.webs.upv.es	UPV
EURESFO	18-20/10/23, Cascais	https://urbanresilienceforum.eu/	RCities, ICLEI

2.1.3 Joint activities with relevant initiatives

UP2030 aspires to establish synergies with other EU projects and international networks/initiatives for outreach actions. Wide visibility and lasting synergies will be pursued by clustering and establishing relations with European/International associations, relevant projects and programmes, as well as initiatives and networks and other cross-cutting themes and activities in EU and world-wide.

The collaboration with the projects of the same cluster plays a crucial role in this effort. Specifically, UP2030 participated in the two Urban Planning and Design Cluster Meetings that were held on 6th- 7th of February 2023 and on 28th of June 2023 in Brussels. The projects that participated were the projects from the same call [Climaborough](#), [Re-value](#), and the Horizon Mission Cities platform [NetZeroCities \(NZC\)](#). Main discussion topics were the potential technical and scientific synergies between the living labs and projects and additional areas of common interest, such as methodology, visualisation techniques, etc. Furthermore, a common ground was established in terms of bringing evaluation approaches within NZC and the cluster and communication opportunities through the NetZero Cities platform and knowledge Repository.

Furthermore, UP2030 participated in the second annual event for the EU Mission for Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities Mission on the 26th - 27th of June 2023 in Brussels. In this event, City mayors, political representatives and practitioners, European Commission officers, national authorities, the Mission Platform NZC and other relevant stakeholders participated in an aim to connect and engage on Mission-critical concepts and ideas.

2.1.4 Publications

In order to promote the widespread recognition of the project's achievements within the research community and facilitate their long-term adoption, it is crucial to publish these concepts in esteemed

conferences and journals. The consortium anticipates that the project, considering the publication academic, scientific and research background of its partners, will generate at least fifty (50) publications. Nevertheless, instead of solely emphasizing the quantity of publications, the project will prioritise their quality of journals and their impact. To ensure their quality and their impact databases like Scopus provide comprehensive coverage of scientific literature and can be used to search for articles, check citation counts, and analyze the impact of specific journals or publications. In addition, conferences often have a peer review process to assess the quality and relevance of submitted papers.

UP2030 will utilise scientific publications as a means of disseminating its technical knowledge and scientific accomplishments. Simultaneously, the dissemination of technical results will occur through various channels, including blog posts, articles, position/white papers, catalogs, books, and other platforms relevant to technology providers. Additionally, publications focusing on the case study domains being examined will also be utilised for this purpose.

The consortium has agreed on an initial publication strategy and significant attempts are being made to accelerate the efforts. Since this document is reporting activities completed until M6, there are no articles or documents published yet. Nevertheless, in D6.4 "Report on Dissemination and Communication actions and their impact 2" is expected that the first publications will be reported and updated information will be included regarding the planned ones.

2.2 Individual dissemination plans

Table 3 includes the individual dissemination plans in terms of D&C activities and channels that UP2030 consortium intends to utilize. These plans will be updated every three months and in the D6.2 "Dissemination and Communication strategy 2" on M15 an updated version will be presented. The dissemination activities of the partners are monitored according to these plans. The symbol "X" declares that the partner plan to proceed with the relevant activity. In the table there are symbols "X" that enclose the link of the activities that have been already conducted.

Table 3 Individual Dissemination plans

Partner	Partners website	Twitter Post	LinkedIn Post	Facebook Post	Newsletter	Publication	Event Participation
FRAUNHOFER	X		X		X	X	X
ADELPHI	X						
BH	X	X	X	X	X		
DC			X				X
GreenAdapt	X	X	X				
ICA	X	X	X				X
ISOCARP	X		X		X		
TSPA	X	X	X	X	X		X

TUD							
UIC	X		X				X
GGGI			X				X
ICLEI	<u>X</u>	X	X		X		X
RCities	X	X	X		X		X
UCCRN	<u>X</u>		X		X		X
AQUATEC	X	X	X				
CETAQUA	X	X	X				
LIF	<u>X</u>	X	X	X			
LNEC							
MDAT	<u>X</u>	X	X	X	X		X
METU	X	X	X				X
USTUTT						X	X
VUB	<u>X</u>					X	X
CERTH							
CIRCE		X	X	X			
DELTARES							
DRAXIS	X		X	X			
DReVen	X		X	X			
GUNAM	<u>X</u>		X		X		
K3Y	<u>X</u>	X	X	X	X		
LINKS							X
MAG		X	X	X			
UPV	<u>X</u>					X	X

VM	X		X	X	X	X	X
Budapest	X			X	X		X
Granollers	<u>X</u>	X		X	<u>X</u>		X
Istanbul	<u>X</u>	X		X		X	X
Lisbon	<u>X</u>	X	X	X			X
E-NOVA	X	X	X	X	X		X
Milan							
Muenster	<u>X</u>			X	X		X
Rotterdam	<u>X</u>	X	X		<u>X</u>		X
Thessaloniki		X	X				X
Zagreb	<u>X</u>	X		X		X	X
ETH	X	X	X		X	X	X
MfC	<u>X</u>	X	X	X	<u>X</u>	X	X
UCAM							
Belfast	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

3 Communication tools and activities

The project's visual identity aspires to facilitate dissemination activities and ensure consistency in the communication of UP2030's concept, objectives, and results. From the first months of the project, the logo, the colour palette and the communication kit were designed and distributed to all partners to be used throughout the lifespan of UP2030. D6.1 "Dissemination and Communication Strategy" presented also the project templates and the social media banners created as long as the guidelines for the usage of these materials.

3.1 UP2030 Logo and Colour Palette

3.1.1 Colour Palette

It is evident that colours increase the recognition of a project and a brand in general. Based on CCICOLOR,¹ the average person makes a subconscious judgment about a product within the first 90 seconds based on colour alone.² For this reason, the D&C team of UP2030 attempted to convene in a colour coding that supports the branding and identify the project easier. Furthermore, inclusivity is reflected on it, since research was conducted to identify colours that are accessible to all and thus decided upon the following 3-colour-palette:

Figure 16 UP2030 Color Palette

The colour palette -Figure 16- was selected to catch people's attention and radiate vividness, optimism, and trustworthiness. It is meant to represent the brightness and sprightliness of the ideas and solutions to be developed within the project. This colour palette will be used for all purposes relevant to the project, from dissemination materials to project deliverables.

3.1.2 UP2030 Logo

The logo will play an essential role in the visual identity of the project. It will be reflected in all external communication activities, such as materials, participation in events, etc., as it is the main visual messenger of the project, and facilitating its recognition instantly by external stakeholders. The logo - Figure 17 - was uploaded to the UP2030 MS Teams Sharepoint folders of UP2030 to be easily accessible by all partners.

¹ <https://ccicolor.com/>

² COLORCOM, Why Color Matters (2019), <https://www.colorcom.com/research/why-color-matters>

Figure 17 UP2030 Logo

In addition, a simplified version of the logo was designed - as shown in Figure 18- to facilitate the usage of the logo in materials that the first version might not fit, for instance in a white page. Partners should determine when and where it is appropriate to use each logo, but they should always ensure that they use the right size and resolution for their activities. Moreover, the logo should not be altered in any way.

Figure 18 UP2030 Logo - simplified version

3.2 [Communication Kit](#)

A communication kit has been designed – M5- according to the visual guidelines of the project as they are described in the D6.1. It has been distributed to all partners by DreVen, the WP6 and D&C communication leaders. It includes information about the project through a **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**, a **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**, and a **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** UP2030's consortium decided during the GA preparation to prepare different types of promotional material aiming to reach all target audiences. The press kit is distributed to stakeholders in digital form, as well as in printed copies if needed. As the project aims for climate-neutrality in cities printed copies will be limited and provided only if needed, so to reduce the environmental impact of the project.

3.2.1 [Poster](#)

A poster constitutes a single piece of paper aiming to catch the attention of the general public and provide information and spread awareness about a project. Posters can be used in different occasions for different purposes. For example, they can be advertising posters aiming to promote the project and draw the general public's attention, or they can be informative and used to educate and influence individuals about the project. The latter mainly target stakeholders who could benefit from the results and findings of this project.

The first poster of UP2030 falls into the category of advertising posters and includes essential information about the project, such as the title, a short summary, and where the proposed solutions will be tested. In addition, the partners’ logos and the EU emblem are also displayed. The poster can be used in any event the consortium organises or takes part in with the aim of successfully advertising the project by bringing attention to it. There is also the possibility that the partners will participate in events where specific posters may be required and DreVen, as WP6 leader, can support them in their preparation.

Figure 19 UP2030 poster

3.2.2 Brochure

A simple and catchy tri-fold brochure was prepared by DreVen. The brochure aims to facilitate the reader to scan through the information of the project. It includes brief information about the project scope, as well as the use-cases where the outcomes will be pilot-tested. Moreover, the brochure aims to attract people’s attention, encouraging them to visit UP2030’s website and social media accounts and to overall stay up-to-date with the innovations the project is offering. Similar to the poster, the brochure targets any relevant stakeholder, as it is easy to understand and provides information about UP2030 at a glance. In addition, since one of the main objectives of the UP2030 D&C actions is to keep the ecological impact at the lowest level possible, the brochure will be printed and distributed only for promotional purposes in external events (e.g., conferences, meetings, etc.)

Figure 20 UP2030 Brochure

3.2.3 Roll-up Banner

A roll-up banner was created to be utilised in events, workshops and other occasions where UP2030 should have a distinct presence. It is feasible to customise the content of the banner, for instance, to add the title of the event or the name of the pilot city the partner wishes to focus.

Figure 21 UP2030 Roll-up banner

3.3 [Project website](#)

3.3.1 [Project website structure](#)

The UP2030 project's website was launched on M3 and serves as a primary platform for promoting the project and keeping stakeholders informed about its progress, outcomes, and results. Figure 22 illustrates the landing page of the UP2030 website, while you can access the website through the following link: <https://up2030-he.eu/>.

Figure 22 UP2030 website

The website has a user-friendly structure, where each page is designed to match the project's color palette as described in 3.1.1 Colour Palette. To enhance its visual appeal, vibrant pictures that complement the colors were incorporated on every page. In every page of the website the logo of the project is displayed in the upper left corner to enable the visitors return to the home page. A navigation bar with tabs and sub-tabs provides easy access to the desired page. The footer is also the same for every page and includes a section to subscribe to the UP2030 newsletter, the UP2030's funding statement, links to the social media accounts of the project and the Privacy Policy that applies to the use of the website.

Figure 23 UP2030 Website footer

Importantly, the project's website is also responsive and can be viewed on mobile devices. This section provides an overview of the website's initial layout.

The UP2030 website consists of the following pages:

- [Home](#)
- [About](#)
 - [UP2030 Project](#)
 - [EU Cities Mission](#)
 - [Relevant Initiatives](#)
- [Pilot Cities](#)

- [Belfast](#)
- [Budapest](#)
- [Granollers](#)
- [Istanbul](#)
- [Lisbon](#)
- [Milan](#)
- [Muenster](#)
- [Rio de Janeiro](#)
- [Rotterdam](#)
- [Thessaloniki](#)
- [Zagreb](#)
- [Library](#)
 - [Publications](#)
 - [Deliverables](#)
 - [Communication Kit](#)
- [Consortium](#)
- [News & Events](#)
- [Contact us](#)

3.3.2 [Project website content](#)

The primary purpose of UP2030's website is to offer comprehensive information regarding the project's advancements and achievements. Consequently, it will undergo regular updates to ensure the dissemination of the latest developments. Serving as a vital communication tool, the website plays a crucial role in effectively promoting UP2030 to its intended target audiences and stakeholders.

The website's structure is designed to provide visitors with essential details regarding the project's objectives, upcoming activities, and ongoing progress. Additionally, visitors can access all publicly available project deliverables, documents, and other dissemination materials that will be created throughout the project's duration. The website also presents pertinent information such as news and events, fostering stakeholder engagement.

- **The homepage** of the website includes the overview of the project. The visitor has the chance to be informed in high-level about UP2030's objectives, the use cases, the European Union (EU) Mission Climate Neutral and Smart Cities, to which the project is related and the latest news and events of the project.

Figure 24 UP2030 Website homepage

- The UP2030 project page consists of more detailed information about UP2030. Here, the project is presented in a glance, as well as the 5UP approach to accelerate the implementation of the activities in all project phases and the solutions.

Figure 25 UP2030 Website project page

- The EU Cities Mission page is dedicated to the EU Mission Climate Neutral and Smart Cities.

Figure 26 UP2030 Website EU Cities Mission page

- The **Relevant Initiatives** page presents the projects and the initiatives that are related to the project and includes the links for the projects from the same cluster. This page will be updated during the lifespan of UP2030 as long as new collaborations and synergies with relevant initiatives will occur.

Figure 27 UP2030 Website Relevant Initiatives page

- The **Pilot Cities** page includes a map of the cities of the project and a separate box for each city, with a photo and the name of the city. This box is clickable and navigates the user to the dedicated page

for each pilot city. In this page are enclosed information about the challenges and the objectives to be achieved through UP2030 for the pilot city.

Figure 28 UP2030 Website Pilot Cities page

- **The Library page** encloses the page of Publications, Deliverables and Communication Kit. The materials will be uploaded appropriately to the related page when new items are prepared in these sections.

Figure 29 UP2030 Website Library page

- **The Consortium page** includes information for all partners, their logo, a short description and the direct link to their website. The 47 partners are divided into three categories: research and innovation partners, technology partners and cities in order to facilitate the user in navigating.

Figure 30 UP2030 Website Consortium page

- **The News & Events page** presents the compilation of events in which project partners have either participated or organized, showcasing the project's progress. Additionally, upcoming events related to the topics covered by UP2030 are listed, aiming to assist stakeholders in finding conferences, workshops, and other relevant gatherings.

Figure 31 UP2030 Website News & Events page

- **The Contact Us page** presents the contact details of the project coordinator and the contact form. The messages from the contact form are received by the D&C team of UP2030 and they reply to them or forward them to the relevant contact person.

Figure 32 UP2030 Website Contact page

DreVen is responsible for the continuous updating of the website's content. All project partners are encouraged to contribute material related to their respective tasks to enhance the website's information pool. As mentioned, below, the blog page on the website will be refreshed on a monthly basis. The overall performance of the website by M6 is presented in the Figure 33.

Figure 33 UP2030 Website performance by M6

3.4 Social media presence

The UP2030 project maintains account in [LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#). The dissemination process will heavily rely on the significant involvement of social media. These accounts are updated every week by DreVen. The content of the posts is related to the ongoing activities of the project the current week. DreVen asks input from the partners regarding the content to appropriately disseminate their activities in the social media accounts of UP2030. The post planning and identification of the most relevant content is facilitated by the event calendar created in the UP2030 MS Teams SharePoint.

Figure 34 UP2030 LinkedIn account

Figure 35 UP2030 Twitter account

3.4.1 Social media performance

The LinkedIn account of UP2030 has gained 374 followers by M6. Figure 36 presents some Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) regarding the 753 visitors of the LinkedIn page of the project from M3 to M6.

Figure 36 UP2030 LinkedIn visitors

The Twitter account of UP2030 has earned 1.6K impressions by M6 as presented in Figure 37.

Figure 37 UP2030 Twitter impressions

In addition, individual partners perform a remarkable effort to disseminate the project in their own social media accounts either by reposting the posts of UP2030 accounts or by creating their own posts. The tables below present the individual partners’ posts for UP2030 in the most popular social media platforms, i.e., Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter.

Table 4 Individual partners Facebook posts

Facebook			
Account	Date	Engagement	Link
LIF	21/04/23	85 impressions	https://m.facebook.com/story.php?story_fbid=pfbid0kAh6pxNWUNSArKp7zFbtew6gCsrVYrdnDDjvLmnvACq7FBJsCAZKnnrmpSwYsNgqI&id=100069042942457
VUB	05/06/2023	n/ a	https://www.facebook.com/imecsmitvub
K3Y	24/02/23	Impressions: 35, Reach: 26, Engagement: 6	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid022H6Q6ytDbrnRcn21xVSkZdG6oKdZyLqTcib6FMCzFvBP4LCUcMu5EivtsXB0xDJDI&id=100063501224733
K3Y	02/06/23	n/a	https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid0vBam981FfjXRF9QhNGPj9mfWZftAwYLRzZopS2uNJMTNs3qQ4eHzoaSuFMMsCL8I&id=100063501224733
Koupkas Michalis (Thessaloniki)	01/02/2023	192 reactions, 3 shares	https://www.facebook.com/koupkas/posts/pfbid02zs5STG6cUxWKQhP7xu2NtUTomJywn7xFtznHsZv78JZzDzuSbiVyL8WyePr27vYqI

MDAT SA	31/05/2023	12 reactions, 3 shares	https://www.facebook.com/mdaThessaloniki/posts/pfbid02HYgSSbEAX4dbkN3aZV51omfc5DAPQQzcunJKDPBg1znNZ636LwuqAEG4ZMsjxvgnl
TSPA	03/02/2023	2 likes	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=729440668821648&set=a.589935186105531
Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality	05/2023	4 Likes	https://www.facebook.com/100072460985985/posts/pfbid0J3WiyKNqUQQiTBHMic9uqYg26XJGuwXWXYqWhtgJaEPBn4ib9JitJM3uY925791ul/?mibextid=if9HGS
Lisboa E-Nova	10/03/2023	98 visualizations 1 reaction 0 shares	https://www.facebook.com/LisboaENova/posts/pfbid0ud5mk6QDxwX7ZcsyeYuPiCVAqXVvQrBfGfV2eZoCyJrRstfQ8KYjXSGvNysj6ol
Lisboa E-Nova	23/03/2023	160 visualizations 5 reactions 0 shares	https://www.facebook.com/LisboaENova/posts/pfbid0ANovC46Z9d5x7baCUcMkgC7tdgAMjUyXynLkmUn8vYGdLHh8PFgkgLDXQFHSRnWl
Lisboa E-Nova	29/05/2023	213 visualizations 3 reactions 0 shares	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=564236702554189&set=a.558526809791845

Table 5 Individual partners LinkedIn posts

LinkedIn			
Account	Date	Engagement	Link
Trinidad Fernandez (Fraunhofer)	2/2023	15 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/trinidad-fernandez-85a33172_eu-horizoneu-transport-activity-7030157555536429056-PDFX/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
Trinidad Fernandez (Fraunhofer)	2/2023	109 reactions 6 comments 8 repost	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/trinidad-fernandez-85a33172_up2030-horizoneurope-missioncities-activity-7027367688536518656-qj2m/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
Constanza Vera (Fraunhofer)	2/2023	4 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/constanza-vera_up2030-horizoneurope-missioncities-activity-7027371505936138240-lqs?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
Fraunhofer IAO	4/2023	50 reactions 3 comments 3 reposts	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/fraunhofer-iao_emissionen-klimaneutralitaet-klimaneutralitaet-activity-7049658702773018624-

			30d9?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
Steffen Braun (Fraunhofer)	4/2023	3 comments 15 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/steffen-braun-405b2812b_emissionen-klimaneutralitaet-klimaneutralitaet-activity-7049807150319067136-t_CX?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
Steffen Braun (Fraunhofer)	2/2023	1 comment 18 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/steffen-braun-405b2812b_up2030-horizoneurope-missioncities-activity-7027532829659910145-MieQ/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
Adelphi	2/2023	24 Likes 1 comment 1 share	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/adelphi_carbonzero-resilientcities-climateadaptation-activity-7028385472687079424-42XI/
Adelphi	4/2023	66 Likes 3 comments 25 shares	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7047507057628844032?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
Buro Happold	24/05/2023	81 reactions, 5 shares	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/buro-happold_up2030-activity-7067099415575982082-PcJP/?originalSubdomain=ch
ICATALIST / Sara	31/03/2023	353 views, 4 reactions, 0 shares	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ing-sara-ros-car2o_granollers-icatalist-activity-7047517296407244800-40B6?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
ICATALIST account	30/03/2023	220 views, 8 reactions, 90 clicks, 45.45% interaction rate 1 share	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7047478696567291905?updateEntityUrn=urn%3Ali%3Afs_feedUpdate%3A%28V2%2Curn%3Ali%3AActivity%3A7047478696567291905%29
ICATALIST / Sara Ros	27/02/2023	283 views, 4 reactions, 0 shares	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ing-sara-ros-car2o_urban-planning-and-design-ready-for-2030-activity-7024732225090764801-KQ1-?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
ICATALIST account	27/01/2023	506 views, 13 reactions, 22 clicks, 7,31% interaction rate 2 shares	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7024723507976544257?updateEntityUrn=urn%3Ali%3Afs_feedUpdate%3A%28V2%2Curn%3Ali%3AActivity%3A7024723507976544257%29
ISOCARP Institute	2/2023	14 Likes, 1 Comment	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/isocarp-institute_project-cities-climate-activity-

			7028341489885663232-GfD3/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
Tannya Pico (ISOCARP)	2/2023	41 Likes	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/tannya-pico-nbs_project-cities-climate-activity-7028456507180478465-Qpxs?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
Elena Petsani (ICLEI)	02/2023	56 likes	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/petsanielena_up2030-citiesmission-missiononadaptation-activity-7029130176185659392-mvLr/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
LIF	21/04/23	91 impressions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7055154084164579328/
LIF	31/03/23	77 impressions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7047551187591520256/
LIF	06/02/23	136 impressions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7028387513027239936/
LIF	21/04/23	91 impressions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7055154084164579328/
MDAT	31/05/2023	n/a	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/majordevelopmentagencythessaloniki_asuaseasrasxasb-up2030-asqasnasbasbasjastaxasvashassaspasb-activity-7070305140443930624-odm9?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
Katharina Hölzle (USTUTT)	2/2023	26 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/katharinahoelzle_up2030-horizoneurope-missioncities-activity-7027582828334710786-1f8c/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
VUB	05/06/2023	n/a	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7071392152391421952
VUB	05/06/2023	n/a	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7071392152391421952
Dafni Deligiorgani (DRAXIS)	2/2023	n/a	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/dafni-deligiorgani_project-cities-climate-activity-7028727085942620161-UjbX?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
Dafni Deligiorgani (DRAXIS)	2/2023	n/a	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/dafni-deligiorgani_meeting-brussels-eumissions-activity-7028792354522185728-i_u?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

ODTÜ-GÜNAM	04/2023	2 likes	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/odtugunam_website-project-website-activity-7047583567572258816-IPvh?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
ODTÜ-GÜNAM	05/2023	22 likes – 3 Shares	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/odtugunam_proje-araagntafrma-iagnbirliafbi-activity-7059986678098051074-iGY6?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
Elşen Aydın (ODTÜ-GÜNAM)	05/2023	300 view – 10 likes	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/elsen-aydin-18508a225_proje-araagntafrma-iagnbirliafbi-activity-7060041284685635584-1FDb?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
İpek Güsel Dino (METU)	05/2023	30 Likes	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7062370174238097408?updateEntityUrn=urn%3Ali%3Afs_feedUpdate%3A%28V2%2Curn%3Ali%3Aactivity%3A7062370174238097408%29
Montse Martínez (Aquatec's researcher)	4/2023	34 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7059802487544782849/
VUB	05/06/2023	n/a	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7071392152391421952
K3Y	24/02/23	Unique Impressions: 35, Engagements: 15	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7034882663257681920
K3Y	23/03/23	Unique Impressions: 29, Engagements: 9	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7044630827099467776
K3Y	12/04/23	Unique Impressions: 32, Engagements: 7	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7051841651694075906
K3Y	28/04/23	Unique Impressions: 28, Engagements: 4	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7057671448567414784
K3Y	26/05/23	Unique Impressions: 28, Engagements: 13	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7067790393202872320
K3Y	02/06/23	n/a	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7070402491753861120
Lisboa E-Nova	10/03/2023	594 visualizations 12 reactions 0 shares	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7018527853621194752

Lisboa E-Nova	23/03/2023	143 visualizations 2 reactions 0 shares	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7044635714382143489
Lisboa E-Nova	05/04/2023	230 visualizations 2 reactions 0 shares	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7049402015545790466
Lisboa E-Nova	29/05/2023	305 visualizations 12 reactions 0 shares	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/lisboa-enova-realiza-se-hoje-em-lisboa-o-primeiro-workshop-activity-7068898871740932096-4xVu?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
TSPA	02/02/2023	30 reactions, 2 repost	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7026984300558327810
TSPA	06/02/2023	6 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7028426189115412482
TSPA	31/03/2023	13 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7047527617444405248
UCCRN	01/06/2023	1 reaction	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7069987268198850560/
Thomas Stellmach (TSPA)	02/2023	30 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7026984300558327810?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
Aurelija Matulevičiūtė (TSPA)	02/2023	25 reactions	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/aurelija-matuleviciute_thessaloniki-up2030-urbanplanning-activity-7027182898118033409-yKNE?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
Kinga Feenstra (Rotterdam)	07/02/23	5 comments, 77 reactions, 2878 impressions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7028356649400598528/
Resilient Rotterdam	06/04/23	223 impressions	Repost R-Cities
Rotterdam	10/05/23	24 reactions, 3 shares, 777 impressions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7061985994350174208/
Rotterdam	01/06/23	Posted today	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7070010010507829248
Mapping for Change	31/03/23	2 reactions, 107 impressions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7047527800643166208
Mapping for Change	17/04/23	7. reactions, 1 repost, 213 impressions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7053675486085816320
Mapping for Change	26/04/23	21 reactions, 4 reposts, 336 impressions	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7057001880266108928

Table 6 Individual partners twitter posts

Twitter			
Account	Date	Engagement	Link
Adelphi	31/03/23	8 likes, 7 retweets	https://twitter.com/UP2030_HE/status/1641742220305866754?s=20
ICATALIST account	01/02/2023	99 views, 3 likes, 1 retweet	https://twitter.com/icalist/status/1620759508111986690?s=20
ICATALIST account	27/01/2023	118 views, 3 likes, 1 retweet	https://twitter.com/icalist/status/1619016775290748930?s=20
CETAQUA	03/02/2023	7 likes, 3 retweets	https://twitter.com/CETAQUA/status/1621432716829904897?s=20
LIF	21/04/23	16 views	https://twitter.com/NetLawBG/status/1649388110545932288
LIF	02/02/23	149 views	https://twitter.com/NetLawBG/status/1621046864396288000
Irene Tsakiridou (MDAT)	03/05/2023	63 views 2 likes,	https://twitter.com/IreneTsakiridou/status/1653754354258653187?s=20
VUB	05/06/2023	n/a	https://twitter.com/imec_smit/status/1665627472669425664
K3Y	24/02/23	Impressions: 145, Engagements: 2	https://twitter.com/K3Y_BG/status/1629118064355602435
K3Y	23/03/23	Impressions: 21, Engagements: 1	https://twitter.com/K3Y_BG/status/1638866895763050496
K3Y	12/04/23	Impressions: 66, Engagements: 2	https://twitter.com/K3Y_BG/status/1646076668262469632
K3Y	28/04/23	Impressions: 28, Engagements: 1	https://twitter.com/K3Y_BG/status/1651907165718708227
K3Y	26/05/23	Impressions: 75, Engagements: 1	https://twitter.com/K3Y_BG/status/1662025264312745984
K3Y	02/06/23	n/a	https://twitter.com/K3Y_BG/status/1664638668332572674

TSPA	01/02/2023	15 likes	https://twitter.com/UP2030_HE/status/1620702345305952257/photo/1
TSPA	02/02/2023	10 likes	https://twitter.com/UP2030_HE/status/1621077513429721089/photo/1
TSPA	31/03/2023	8 likes	https://twitter.com/UP2030_HE/status/1641742220305866754/photo/1
Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality	05/2023	19 Likes, 5 Retweets	https://twitter.com/cevreistanbul/status/1654556327140810752?s=20
Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality	05/2023	Retweeted from the account on the first line	https://twitter.com/Istanbulklim
Rotterdam	10/05/23	7 likes, 3 retweets	https://twitter.com/ResilientRdam/status/1656223248302977025
Rotterdam	01/02/23	N/a	Retweets UP2030 https://twitter.com/UP2030_HE/status/1621077513429721089
Mapping for change	01/02/23	213 people reached, 5 likes, 2 retweets	Retweeted from https://twitter.com/Constanza_VeraC/status/1620739726474108930?s=20
Mapping for Change	31/03/23	110 people reached	https://twitter.com/Mapping4Change/status/1641762384111972353?s=20
Mapping for Change	17/04/23	110 people reached	https://twitter.com/Mapping4Change/status/1647989578655989761?s=20
Mapping for Change	27/04/23	249 people reached, 3 retweets, 9 likes	Retweeted from https://twitter.com/UP2030_HE/status/1651547585537032194?s=20

3.5 Newsletter & Press releases

DreVen as WP6 and D&C leader is responsible for moderating the publication of press releases and newsletters. All partners are encouraged to contribute to this effort. DreVen might ask partners to undertake the publication of a press release or a newsletter, with a notice of three weeks, in order to disseminate, for instance, an achievement or progress related to their task etc.

Partners are asked to send the proposed content to be published on the website as a press release to the coordination mailing list < coordination_up2030@draxis.gr > and the WP6 mailing list < wp6_up2030@draxis.gr > and provide feedback and comments within one week. If there is no objection after one week, partners after receiving an informative confirmation e-mail, are capable to proceed with the publication.

3.5.1 Newsletter

Newsletters serve as a highly effective means of promoting stakeholder participation by disseminating project findings, important events, publications, and more. As described in D6.1 ', a dedicated [registration](#)

[form](#) is provided on the project’s website, enabling interested visitors to subscribe to UP2030’s newsletters whenever updates become available.

Figure 38 Newsletter registration form

According to the Grant Agreement (GA), 12 newsletters should be distributed to the registered users. The first two are planned to be distributed by M12; the first one will be related to the workshops that have been held by the pilot cities and the next one will explain the synergies built among UP2030 and the other cluster projects.

3.5.2 Press Release

In order to enhance the project's visibility in the media, the consortium will create at least 4 press releases to communicate significant milestones and interim outcomes of UP2030. These press releases will be shared through the networks of each partner and will also be accessible on the project's website.

Press releases will be translated into the respective language of each partner to facilitate their publication in local media. For this purpose, a list for the responsible partners to translate the dissemination materials to the partners’ native languages -until M15 when this list will be updated - is presented in Table 7. This procedure was followed for the translation of the [first press release](#) of UP2030 project, see Figure 39 Figure 39 1st Press release. The translated materials will be uploaded in specific folder in UP2030 MS Teams Sharepoint folders that will be indicated by DreVen when the partners will be asked to contribute to the translation.

Table 7 Translation list

LANGUAGE	PARTNER
Bulgarian	K3Y
Croatian	Zagreb
Dutch	VUB
German	Fraunhofer
Greek	DRAXIS
Hungarian	GGGI
Italian	UCCRN

Portuguese	LISBOA E-NOVA
Spanish	CIRCE
Turkish	GUNAM

Figure 39 1st Press release

3.6 Blog posts

Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden. Figure 40 presents the blog post timetable and the partner who is responsible to prepare the content for each month, from M6 (June 2023) to M15 (March 2024). On M15, the deliverable D6.2 “Dissemination and Communication strategy 2” will be submitted, in which the table will be updated for the second half of the project. The blog posts will be published in UP2030’s website and disseminated in the social media accounts of the project. DreVen will upload a document in the UP2030 MS Teams Sharepoint and the partners should declare their topic of interest to facilitate the planning and avoid overlapping.

The previous month of the release, DreVen will contact the partner responsible for the blog post of the upcoming month to confirm that the topic chosen is aligned with the project’s progress. The partner responsible for each blog post should submit it to the coordination mailing list and the D&C leader for review, the latest by the 15th of the month that their blog post is planned to be published. The coordination team and the D&C leader should provide their feedback and comments within one week. If there is no objection after one week, partners will be informed that the content of the blog post is ready and it will be published in the project’s website.

Figure 40 Blog post timetable

4 Dissemination and Communication Monitoring

4.1 Dissemination and Communication monitoring files

The project consortium will assess the impact of each D&C channel and activity through the use of reporting templates developed by the D&C leader. DreVen will request all partners to submit quarterly reports detailing the activities they have undertaken to promote UP2030 to relevant stakeholders and the general public. These reports will serve as a means of evaluating the effectiveness of the dissemination activities. Specifically, the monitoring files are the following:

- Dissemination and communication internal partner report.** The aim of this report is to help the D&C leader of the project monitor and collect information about the relevant activities that have been carried out by the consortium partners.

The figure displays three pages of the 'UP2030 Dissemination & Communication Report' template.
 Page 1 (left) is the cover page, featuring the UP2030 logo, the title 'Dissemination & Communication Report', and a placeholder for the partner name: '[PARTNER] - XX/XX/XX'.
 Page 2 (middle) is the introduction and social media accounts section. It includes an 'Introduction' section with instructions on what to include and delete. Below this are two tables: 'Table 1: Dissemination on Facebook' and 'Table 2: Dissemination on LinkedIn'. Both tables have columns for Account, Date, Engagement (reactions, shares), and Link.
 Page 3 (right) is the press release section. It includes 'Table 3: Dissemination on Twitter' with columns for Account, Date, Engagement (replies, retweets, reactions, shares), and Link. Below the table is a 'Press Release' section with instructions and a large placeholder for a screenshot of a prepared press release.

Figure 41 UP2030 Dissemination and Communication Report

UP2030 Individual dissemination plan. In this excel file, all partners are asked to state what types of dissemination activities they will carry out to maximise the impact of UP2030. Partners are strongly encouraged by the D&C team to carry out these activities at least once during the year, except if there is a specific reason not to and which they should communicate with the D&C leader.

Figure 42 UP2030 Individual dissemination plan

UP2030 Publications and events. The purpose of this excel file is to facilitate the better monitoring of the dissemination of the project as regards to publications submitted and participation in various events. In addition, it aims to inform the consortium about future events relevant to the project.

Figure 43 UP2030 Publications and events file

4.2 Dissemination and Communication indicators

The consortium has determined that a range of indicators is suitable for assessing the impact of D&C activities in the project. KPIs will be utilised to evaluate the project's impact. Table 8 and Table 9 outline the indicators planned for the D&C activities and performance since the start of UP2030.

Table 8 Communication activities KPIs.

Communication Activity	KPI	Status by M6
Visual Identity	Prepared in M1	Done
Project website	Online by M3 Unique visitors by M36: >4,000	Done 1,100
Social Media	Number of posts: 1 per week Size of online community by M36: > 4,000	Ongoing 1,600
e-Newsletters and Email Campaigns	Total number of distributed e-Newsletters: 12 Total Mailing List Contact Points: >1,500	Ongoing
Press Releases	Total number of press releases: 4	1
Innovation Portfolio	Number of success stories: story maps for all cities	Not started
Communication Kit	Number of events to be distributed through by end of project >30	Initial materials prepared

Table 9 Dissemination activities KPIs.

Dissemination Activity	KPI	Status by M6
Scientific Publications	Publishing in Peer-Reviewed Journal articles > 30 Presenting in Scientific Conferences > 50 At least 1 special edition led by UP2030 guest editors in a high impact Journal	In progress
Technical Publications	Publishing Technical Publications >20	Not performed yet

	Presenting in Technical Conferences > 20	
Workshops & Trainings	Workshops >10 in 8 different countries Training Tutorials >8; Webinars >10	10 in 8 different countries Not performed yet
Joint Activities with relevant Initiatives	Relevant initiatives to establish links >15 Co-organised events >20 Fairs to Participate >20	In progress
Source Code Repository	Number of Publicly Available Deliverables (24) Source code: publish to >2 different repositories	Not performed yet
Policy briefs	Policy recommendations & best practices > 11 (at least 1 per pilot)	Not performed yet

5 Dissemination and Communication Planned Activities

UP2030 plans to foster its effort to increase the impact of the project efficiently. It is expected that while the project progresses, updates will be presented using following D&C channels, activities and tools, as explained in the previous chapters and in D6.1

The planned activities were described in each section separately. In summary:

- Constant update of website's content
- Launch of the blog page of the website (M6)
- Constant update of social media accounts
- Proceed with scientific and technical publications
- Publication of the first newsletter (until M12)
- Increase the visibility of UP2030 – according to KPIs
- Participation and organization of workshops and events
- Establish new synergies with relevant projects and initiatives
- Development of the Innovation Portfolio

6 Conclusions

The document reflects the report on D&C actions of UP2030 and their impact until the first sixth month of the project. The D&C activities and the relevant management procedures are extensively described. Considerable progress has been made in the relevant tasks according to the planned actions in the D6.1 Dissemination and Communication strategy.

The D&C strategy will be updated in the subsequent deliverable, D6.2, scheduled for March 2024 (M15), led by UCCRN. The execution of this strategy will be closely monitored, and its progress will be reported in the upcoming deliverables:

- D6.4 Report on Dissemination and Communication actions and their impact 2
- D6.5 Report on Dissemination and Communication actions and their impact 3

An updated version of this deliverable (D6.4) will be released in M18 and all adjustments, updates and input based on the experience gained during the first 18 months of UP2030 will be included. Thus, all actions will undergo necessary modifications based on the needs of the project to ensure maximum visibility to the targeted stakeholders and more broadly to the European community.

It is crucial to ensure that all plans will be monitored closely to achieve their successful implementation. The predefined KPIs should be revised bimonthly to estimate if remedial actions are required. It is of great importance to appropriately disseminate the activities performed in the framework of UP2030 and the consortium at this stage is effectively engaged in this effort.

Finally, the D&C activities will prioritize the privacy and anonymity of all participants in UP2030, while adhering to ethical principles, as described in D1.7 - Security, privacy and ethics handbook 1. In the dissemination of research project findings, ensuring the accuracy of the disseminated data is a crucial ethical concern. To address this, the UP2030 project will establish safeguards mechanisms, meticulously collecting and analyzing data. Through this process, the project aims to accurately represent the information when disseminating it through various channels. The smooth implementation of dissemination and communication activities from all partners according to the predefined procedures of UP2030 and their contribution in them are irreplaceable.